

PERIODATES OF COBALT AND NICKEL

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Cobalt sulphate and cobalt nitrate form an iodate of the composition 3CoO_2 , $\text{Co}(\text{IO}_3)_2$, $10\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and a new periodate, cobalt diorthoperiodate, $\text{Co}_2\text{I}_2\text{O}_{11}$, $12\text{H}_2\text{O}$ with disodium paraperiodate and potassium metaperiodate respectively.

Nickel sulphate and nickel chloride form nickel paraperiodate, $\text{Ni}_2(\text{IO}_3)_2$, $13\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and another periodate of the composition, 7NiO , $2\text{I}_2\text{O}_7$, $25\text{H}_2\text{O}$, with disodium paraperiodate and potassium unctaperiodate respectively.

Lautsch (*J. prakt. Chem.*, 1862, 100, 89) obtained a greenish yellow powder of the composition corresponding to 7CoO , $2\text{I}_2\text{O}_7$, by evaporating a solution of disodium paraperiodate with an excess of cobalt sulphate. Rammelsberg (*Ber.*, 1868, 1, 70; *Pogg. Ann.*, 1868, 134, 514, 528) failed to prepare a periodate by the above method, but always obtained a mixture of oxide and an iodate.

In order to elucidate the above discrepancy, the action of disodium paraperiodate on cobalt sulphate was studied and it was found that a greenish brown iodate of the composition, 3CoO_2 , $\text{Co}(\text{IO}_3)_2$, $10\text{H}_2\text{O}$ was obtained. The analyses of the different samples showed it to be of a constant and reproducible composition, therefore it could not be regarded as a mixture of oxide and iodate, as reported by Rammelsberg (*loc. cit.*).

A new periodate of cobalt, cobalt diorthoperiodate, $\text{Co}_2\text{I}_2\text{O}_{11}$, $12\text{H}_2\text{O}$, was obtained by the action of a hot solution of potassium metaperiodate on a solution of cobalt nitrate. The precipitates obtained in both the cases were washed with water and dried in an air-oven at 45° .

E X P E R I M E N T A L

The analyses of the salts were carried out by estimating (i) cobalt by the electrolytic method (Scott, "Standard Methods of Chemical Analysis", 1939, I, 315), (ii) iodine as such by decomposing the salt with heat (Bahl, Singh and Bali, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1943, 19, 587), (iii) available oxygen by the method adopted by Partington and Bahl (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 1086).

TABLE I

Cobalt salt prepared by the action of disodium paraperiodate on cobalt sulphate

Sample.	Cobalt.	Iodine.	O ₂ (available).
1.	27.58%	29.04%	11.15%
2.	27.47	29.48	11.56
3.	27.50	29.11	11.57

TABLE II

Cobalt salt prepared by the action of potassium metaperiodate on cobalt nitrate

Sample.	Cobalt.	Iodine.	O ₂ (available)
1.	25.36%	28.2%	12.67%
2.	25.58	28.4	12.62
3.	25.41	28.0	12.64

The values in Table I agree with the formula of cobalt iodate, CoO_2 , $\text{Co}(\text{IO}_3)_2$, $10\text{H}_2\text{O}$, calculated values being Co, 27.21; I₂, 29.33; O₂(available), 11.01%.

The results in Table II correspond with the formula of cobalt dimesoperiodate, $\text{Co}_2\text{I}_2\text{O}_{11}$, $12\text{H}_2\text{O}$, the calculated values being Co, 25.78; I₂, 27.80; O₂(available), 12.36%.

The Periodates of Nickel

Ramelsberg (*Pogg. Ann.*, 1868, 134, 514) found that a green solution was obtained by the action of periodic acid on nickel carbonate, and a mixture of nickel dioxide, iodate and periodate were left undissolved. The green solution on crystallisation deposited pale green quadratic prisms of the composition, 7NiO , $4\text{I}_2\text{O}_7$, $49\text{-}63\text{ H}_2\text{O}$. Kimmins (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1884, 86, 148) obtained a greenish yellow amorphous precipitate of nickel mesoperiodate, $\text{Ni}_3(\text{IO}_3)_2$, by boiling sodium paraperiodate with a solution of nickel sulphate and a bluish green gelatinous precipitate of nickel dimesoperiodate, $\text{Ni}_2\text{I}_2\text{O}_8$, by treating a solution of potassium dimesoperiodate with nickel sulphate.

It has been found that a light green precipitate of the composition, $\text{Ni}_3(\text{IO}_3)_2$, $13\text{H}_2\text{O}$, is formed by the action of disodium paraperiodate on nickel sulphate and a dirty green precipitate of the composition by the interaction of a hot solution of potassium metaperiodate and nickel chloride. The precipitate in both the cases was filtered, washed with water and dried at 45° in a hot air-oven. The salts were analysed in the same way as in case of cobalt salts given above.

TABLE III

Nickel salt prepared by the action of disodium paraperiodate on nickel sulphate

Sample.	Nickel.	Iodine.	O ₂ (available).
1.	31'01%	27'85%	12'13%
2.	30'89	27'67	12'27
3.	31'27	28'03	12'25
4.	31'23	27'74	12'06

TABLE IV

Nickel salt prepared by the action of potassium metaperiodate on nickel chloride

Nickel.	Iodine.	O ₂ (available).
24'56%	29'88%	12'99%
24'77	29'69	13'52
24'04	29'95	13'27

These results (Table III) agree with the formula of nickel paraperiodate with $\text{Ni}_3(\text{IO}_3)_2$, $13\text{ H}_2\text{O}$, the calculated values being Ni, 31'67%; I₂, 27'50%; O₂(available), 12'12%.

The results in Table IV correspond with the formula $\cdot\text{NiO}$, $2\text{I}_2\text{O}_7$, $25\text{H}_2\text{O}$, the calculated values being Ni, 24'41; I₂, 29'75; available oxygen, 13'13%.

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